

Influence of International Ownership on the Performance of Local Social Enterprises: Evidence from the Global Microfinance Industry

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of international ownership on the performance of social enterprises involved in microfinance. We use a dataset containing 120 shareholder-owned microfinance institutions whereof 54% have shares owned by international investors. Based on international business theories, we hypothesize that international ownership improves both the financial and the social performance of microfinance institutions. However, our results reveal that international owners mostly use their resources and controlling rights to improve social performance at the expense of financial performance. We rely on the hybridity of social enterprises to expound these findings and to draw theoretical and practical implications.

Headings: International Ownership, Corporate Governance, Social Enterprises, Microfinance, Performance

JEL Classification Codes: G21, G23, G32, G34, F23, F65, L31

1. Introduction

This study investigates the influence of international equity investors on the social and financial performance of social enterprises (SEs), i.e., organizations with both social and financial objectives (Mair and Marti 2006). While there is an extensive literature on the impact of international ownership on regular businesses (Doidge et al 2007), we are unaware of any study exploring this phenomenon in the context of SEs. Meanwhile, foreign equity—from both commercial and pro-social investors—plays an important role in the financing of many local SEs. By using global data collected on microfinance institutions (MFIs) incorporated as shareholder-owned firms (SHFs), this study is the first to contribute to this scarce literature.

MFIs are typical examples of SEs (Battilana and Dorado 2010). MFIs provide affordable financial services to poor individuals and small-scale enterprises in emerging markets¹, with the object of assisting these disadvantaged groups to improve their living standards. Given its development potential, the microfinance industry has experienced tremendous growth in recent years, largely due to an increased injection of foreign funds (Reille et al. 2011; Soursourian et al. 2015). Generally, international influence on the industry is significant: Mersland et al. (2011) report that 38% of the MFIs included in their study are initiated by international actors, 51% have international subsidized debt, and 33% are members of recognized international networks, such as the Vision Fund.

The literature has so far not studied the influence of international ownership in microfinance. This is unfortunate since a clear majority of microfinance clients are served by MFIs incorporated as SHFs and not the often-mentioned Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) (Ledgerwood 2013). After all, the ownership influence is potentially much stronger in SHFs compared to NGOs since SHFs are subject to strict governance as owners' fiduciary duties are publicly regulated and owners decide on firms' levels of capitalization (Hansmann 1996). Moreover, shareholders in firms have residual rights and are therefore monetarily motivated to monitor their investees (Hansmann 1996). Currently, in the microfinance industry, more and more NGOs are transforming into regulated shareholder-owned banks (D'Espallier et al. 2017).

Considering the deep influence of shareholders on firms' governance and strategic direction, the little research on international equity investment in SEs is regrettable (Hansmann 1996). For SEs such lack of knowledge could be far-reaching. For example, it has been argued that, investors could potentially endanger SEs to drift away from their core missions by distorting their hybridity through the infusion of unconventional practices (Kent and Dacin 2013). Citing the infamous Andra Pradesh incidence as an

¹ Emerging countries host majority of MFIs worldwide. Yet, some MFIs operate in industrialized countries where they provide banking services to disadvantaged people (Cozarenco and Szafarz, 2014; Pedrini et al. 2016).

example, Ausburg and Fouillet (2010) recounts how international capital providers could push MFIs to drift away from the primary mission making financial services available to poor. As they identified, international capital providers at the time were mainly interested in ensuring that MFIs charge cost-recovery interest rates as well and enhance debt repayment rates (Augsburg and Fouillet 2010).

Several studies of regular markets suggest a positive association between international ownership and local firms' performance. The performance improvements are often attributed to international owners because they bring in knowledge (Dunning 2000) or improve access to funding, which can decrease the cost of capital (e.g., Hearn et al. 2010; Randøy et al. 2001). These findings may not necessarily hold for SEs such as MFIs. For SEs, performance is a more complex concept than for traditional banks and other corporations (Battilana and Dorado 2010). SEs typically subscribe to the dual objectives of financial sustainability and social welfare. Importantly, for SEs, the association between foreign ownership and firm performance can be multidimensional. For instance, it is possible that increased access to international capital can enhance social performance and impair financial performance (Mersland et al. 2011), or vice versa. The policy implications of foreign ownership are thus less straightforward for SEs than for regular corporations. The microfinance industry is characterized by a rapidly increasing proportion of international investments (Soursourian et al. 2015) that are mostly channeled through investment funds known as microfinance investment vehicles (MIVs). In most cases, MIVs manage debt and equity funds provided by socially responsible private individuals and institutions (mostly originating from the global North) that are interested in promoting financial inclusion in emerging markets (Briere and Szafarz, 2015; Cobb et al. 2016; Dorfleitner et al. 2017). Thus, the microfinance industry is characterized by large cultural and geographical distances between capital providers and investees operating with locally rooted business models (Lensink et al. 2008). Consequently, the potential advantages of foreign ownership may be hampered by liability of foreignness (Peng et al. 2008; Masulis et al. 2012).

Our dataset comprises of data on 120 shareholder-owned MFIs whereof 54.2 percent are wholly or partially owned by international shareholders while the remainder are owned only by local shareholders. We operationalize international ownership as the percentage of stake held by the international owner(s). The results show that, on the one hand, international ownership positively impacts, portfolio quality and outreach to low-income clients who are predominantly women. On the other hand, international ownership appears to have a negative impact on return on equity due to larger operating expenses in MFIs that have foreign owners. We rely on the hybridity of SEs to expound these findings and to draw theoretical and practical implications.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the research context and relevant literature and presents the theory and research hypotheses. Section 3 describes the data and research methods. Sections

4 and 5 present and discuss the results, respectively. Section 6 concludes and highlights some policy and academic implications.

2. Research Setting, Literature, and Hypotheses

2.1. The microfinance context

In the early stages of the industry's development, MFIs were primarily nonprofit establishments incorporated as NGOs and supported by donations, grants, and subsidies (Hudon and Traca 2011). Essentially, these institutions were concerned with giving out small loans to poor individuals, especially women (Servin et al. 2012). Subsequently, the microfinance industry entered a new phase, serving wealthier clients with bigger loans. Some observers consider microfinance to be evolving gradually into a more commercialized banking industry (D'Espallier et al. 2017; Lützenkirchen and Weistroffer 2012) that mobilizes funds from market sources (Servin et al. 2012).

MFIs are now financed by a mix of donations, deposits from clients, equity, and debt, with a significant proportion of the latter two sources originating from international impact investors (Lützenkirchen and Weistroffer 2012; Mersland et al. 2020). While the majority of international funding to microfinance comes in the form of debt, an increasing share of the investments are directed as equity capital to shareholder-owned MFIs (Briere and Szarfaz 2015).

Overall, the growth of the microfinance industry has been impressive, thanks to the influx of foreign funds. Reille et al. (2011, p.1) recount that “even with the financial crisis in the four years preceding 2011, foreign investment in microfinance, including both debt and equity, quadrupled to reach US\$ 13 billion as of 2010.” In the years that followed, the strong growth of the microfinance industry continued, with international funding reaching US\$ 31 billion in 2014 (Soursourian et al. 2015). Despite the high growth of the industry it is still estimated that about 2.3 billion people and 200 million formal and informal micro, small and medium enterprises in emerging markets remain without access to banking services (ResponsAbility 2017). According to Lahaye (2016),² equity holders in MFIs influence the management of investees by means of three leverage points: entry, governance, and exit. At the entry level, equity investors decide which MFIs to invest in. Thus, their decisions have a direct influence on where more or fewer clients will be served (Berger et al. 2009). At the governance level, equity investors may also influence MFI performance by being actively involved in the development and monitoring of the investee (Bruton et al. 2010). At the exit level, an exit decision by an investor results in a change of

² The Lahaye (2016) report is of particular relevance since the publisher is CGAP, which is the microfinance branch of the World Bank. As the leading microfinance “think tank” for the past 25 years, CGAP has had an important influence on the development of the microfinance industry.

ownership that can possibly alter the business's strategy and the mode of the market's development. Consequently, exit, a possibility that does not exist in NGOs, is considered an important control mechanism in the governance literature (Ackerman 2004; Bharath et al. 2013; Mersland 2009).

2.2. Theoretical foundations and prior research

Departing from the general international business literature, the main theoretical bases for this study are agency theory, resource-based theory, and the liability of foreignness perspective. Proponents of *agency theory* argue for a well-structured board of directors whose main duty is to protect the interests of the firm's owners by formulating the strategic plans of the firm and monitoring its implementation by the management (Jensen and Meckling 1976; Fama and Jensen, 1983). In general, suppliers of finance minimize agency costs and assure themselves of their investment returns through corporate governance (Shleifer and Vishny 1997; Strange et al. 2009). Building on this, Hartarska (2005, p. 1628) defines governance in microfinance as "the mechanisms through which donors, equity investors, and other providers of funds assure themselves that their funds will be used according to the intended purposes."

Using data on 11 transition countries, Bonin et al. (2009) find that foreign ownership has a positive impact on profitability and efficiency. Similarly, using a Chinese database, Berger et al. (2009) find that even with minority ownership, foreign investors are able to influence performance positively. Evidence shows that foreign investors often install stricter risk-monitoring mechanisms aimed at safeguarding their investments (García-Herrero and Santabárbara 2008). These studies from traditional industries support agency theory-based predictions of a positive relationship between foreign equity ownership and performance.

Scholars of *resource-based theory* stress that foreign institutional investors often bring to the table superior risk-management skills and technologies that improve corporate governance (García-Herrero and Santabárbara 2008). In addition, these investors sometimes serve as links to sources where firms can tap into more efficient strategic and operational practices (Yoshikawa and Phan, 2001, 2003; Gulamhussen and Guerreiro 2009). Moreover, international investments may be associated with lower costs of capital (Hearn et al. 2010; Randøy et al. 2001). From a *resource-based theory* perspective, therefore, international ownership serves as a useful organizational resource that underpins a competitive advantage (Barney 1991).

In accordance with agency and resource-based theories, several empirical international business studies find a positive impact of internationalization on firm performance (Ruigrok and Wagner 2003; Ruigrok et al. 2007). These benefits stem from four prominent areas: (i) economies of scale (Dunning, 2000; Manolova et al. 2010), (ii) reduced cross-border agency costs through internalized markets

(Buckley and Casson 1998), (iii) lower costs of capital (Hearn et al. 2010; Oxelheim et al. 2001), and (iv) better corporate governance (Oxelheim and Randøy 2003).

However, it remains an open question in the international business literature whether agency theory and resource-based theory provide valid frameworks for studying SEs as well. Do the so-called international investors use their resources and controlling rights to influence mostly the financial or the social performance of their investees? Essentially, the traditional agency-cost theory rests on the assumption that owners in mainstream organizations consider profit maximization as the central objective. However, in their multitask principal-agent model, Holmstrom and Milgrom (1991) demonstrated how the conventional principal-agent model may not provide useful guidance in designing incentive-monitoring systems, especially at a time when business objectives are becoming increasingly multidimensional.

Another factor challenging the agency and resource-based predictions relates to the potential cost disadvantages associated with foreign ownership (Williams and Nguyen 2005), particularly when the geographical and cultural distance between the investor and the investee is great (Rugman et al. 2011), as is the case in microfinance. In fact, the impact of international ownership on performance may be negative owing to *liability of foreignness*. Miller and Parkhe (2002) argue that liability of foreignness—i.e. the costs and other disadvantages associated with international investment (Hymer 1976; Zaheer and Mosakowski, 1997)—exists in banking and other industries.

In the regular banking industry, some studies have found that foreign ownership improves overall profitability and efficiency (Berger et al. 2009; Lin and Zhang 2009; Bonin et al. 2005) and is associated with the implementation of repayment-enhancing policies (Crystal et al. 2002). Other positive effects include governance improvements and access to capital (García-Herrero and Santabárbara, 2008; Heugens et al. 2009). However, in line with the somewhat contradictory theoretical predictions discussed earlier, some studies document a *negative* influence of foreign ownership on bank performance (Berger et al. 2005; Unite and Sullivan 2003). Lensink et al. (2008) note that the negative effect of foreign ownership is worse in countries with bad governance practices—which is precisely the setting in which most MFIs operate.

Overall, the evidence—both theoretical and empirical—on the relationship between international ownership and firm performance in mainstream banking and other industries is mixed. In what follows we develop hypotheses on the influence of foreign ownership on the social and financial performance of local microfinance SHFs.

2.3. Hypothesis development

In line with Lensink et al. (2008) who found a negative impact of foreign ownership on the efficiency of regular banks, we argue that MFIs with international owners may incur similar operational inefficiencies. This is because most international equity investors prefer to invest in MFIs that target poor customers in geographical areas plagued with weak market institutions (Briere and Szarfarsz 2015). In most of the markets where MFIs operate, unfriendly business institutions, including weak regulatory systems, weak judicial systems, and corruption, often inflate the cost of doing business. Overall, as liability of foreignness is associated with lower profitability even in regular markets (see also Lu and Beamish 2004), it is not unreasonable to contend that MFIs that have international owners may exhibit low performance compared to those that do not have international owners. Mersland and Strøm (2009) specifically note that international directors could represent a cost factor as they are likely to bring on board a costly culture that negatively affects financial performance.

However, several other studies point to a positive influence of international ownership on the financial performance of MFIs. Hartarska (2005) argues that international shareholders can improve financial performance through the promotion of governance-enhancing mechanisms such as board independence (see also Mori et al. 2015). In this regard, Lahaye (2016) document how equity investors enhance the monitoring and advisory roles of the board. Moreover, in their recent study, Cobb et al. (2016) suggest that, irrespective of the source of investor funding flowing into an MFI (commercial or public source), impact investors are more likely to allocate their scarce resources to larger MFIs that are more resilient to adverse political and financial situations (see also Dobrev et al. 2003; Ausburg and Fouillet 2010). The implication is that international equity investors may influence MFIs to extensively focus on financial objectives.

Following our earlier arguments that international owners, because of their fiduciary duties and rights to residuals (Hansmann 1996), have a greater possibility of influencing MFI's financial outcomes positively, we observe that a number of internationally owned MFIs are sold off after years of operation. For instance, in 2008 two Ugandan MFIs, namely, Ugandan Microfinance Limited and Commercial Microfinance Limited, were acquired by the Equity Bank of Kenya and the Nigeria-based Global Trust Bank, respectively. Again, in 2009 Financiera Edyficar, a Peru-based microfinance group founded by the non-governmental organization, CARE, sold over 70% of its shares to the Peruvian commercial bank, Banco de Credito. Another example is the selling off of many MFIs, including Compartamos in Mexico, by USA based ACCION International.

Thus, we can expect socially oriented international investors to be concerned about the financial performance of their investees because the greater the financial health of the investees, the greater the amount of wealth the investors can accumulate if they choose to sell their investments, *ceteris paribus*. In

return, this will influence more investments elsewhere in the future. More so, microfinance equity investors are not philanthropists. Aside investing in pro-social organizations, such investors adhere to standard portfolio theory to maximize their financial returns (Cobb et al. 2016). Overall, while the financial performance of internationally owned MFIs could be impaired by the cost disadvantages associated with liability of foreignness, we expect international ownership to elicit an overall positive financial performance because of its drive to accumulate more wealth for more future investments. Thus, we formulate the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1. International ownership has a positive impact on the financial performance of MFIs.

Although the literature on the relationship between internationalization and the social performance of MFIs is scarce, there is nevertheless evidence to suggest that this relationship is somewhat less ambiguous than the relationship between internationalization and the *financial* performance of MFIs. As mentioned above, Mersland et al. (2011) find a positive effect of internationalization on the social performance of MFIs. Specifically, they find that MFIs with more international stakeholders focus more on vulnerable clients like women and rural families than locally oriented MFIs.

Though former studies like Mersland et al. (2011) focus on international stakeholders and NGOs we assume ex ante that international investors owning equity stake in MFIs are interested in the social mission of microfinance. As observed by Briere and Szafarz (2015), microfinance is a useful tool for investors interested in the welfare of poor people in emerging economies. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: International ownership has a positive impact on the social performance of MFIs.

It should be noted that several microfinance studies suggest that there is a trade-off between the financial and social performance of MFIs (Hermes et al. 2011; Cull et al. 2007). Specifically, outreach to vulnerable clients is expensive and may harm financial results (Cull et al. 2007). However, the trade-off may go in the opposite direction as well. The strong growth of microfinance is stimulated by the entry of more commercial players into the industry (Lützenkirchen and Weistroffer 2012). Such investors might be more concerned about financial returns on their investments than outreach to vulnerable people (Briere and Szafarz, 2015). In such cases, international investors may be associated with improved financial performance at the expense of social performance. Similarly, as mentioned above, international equity investors may be particularly concerned with the market value of their shares because when exiting the investee, they can reinvest resources in new ventures with potentially higher social returns. Thus, we cannot rule out that the direction of Hypothesis 2 is the opposite of what we suggest.

Nonetheless, if a positive association between international ownership and performance (financial or social) is found in the microfinance industry, the reader should be aware that the causality of the association is not obvious. International private equity investors usually invest in specialized equity funds “which then channel the invested funds to MFIs” (Lützenkirchen and Weistroffer 2012, p. 8). In a way, these MIVs serve as specialized capital markets for the microfinance industry (Mersland and Urgeghe 2013). According to Wiesner and Quien (2010) and Mersland and Urgeghe (2013), MIVs often prefer to invest in regulated and well-monitored MFIs. MIVs therefore concentrate on funding MFIs that are efficient and financially sound (Wiesner and Quien, 2010). We return to this issue of possible endogeneity in the next section.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data

In this study, we use data on 120 share-issuing MFIs, none of them publicly listed,³ operating in 40 countries. The unique dataset consists of hand-collected information gathered from rating reports published by the five leading microfinance rating agencies: Microrate, Microfinanza, Planet Rating, CRISIL, and M-CRIL. The rating reports were downloaded from the former website of the rating fund (www.ratingfund2.org) or obtained directly from the rating agencies. The rating reports provide data on the MFIs for the period between 1999 and 2014, with the majority of the reports taken from the second half of this period. Since the rating agencies do not follow a standard reporting format, the dataset has varying number of observations on the different variables. The maximum number of firm-year observations are 526. Hence the data is unbalanced with the average MFI having approximately five observations over the period under study. The rating reports categorize the MFIs along several dimensions, including their legal structure and whether they have an international shareholder. In most cases the names of the large international shareholders are mentioned in the reports. Additionally, we retrieve from the raw data a large number of variables that are relevant for studying internationalization and financial and social performance (more on these variables below). A strength of our study is that all our data are gathered by professional and independent third parties and are not self-reported by MFIs.

³ In fact, only about 10 MFIs in the world are publicly listed (Briere and Szafarz 2015).

3.2 Model estimation

The goal of this survey is to explore how international ownership (independent variable) affects MFIs' financial and social performance (dependent variables). Table 1 presents the list of dependent, independent, and control variables used in the study. We test our hypotheses with variables that have been used in previous empirical microfinance studies, such as Briere and Szafarz (2015), Tchakoute-Tchuigoua (2010), and Mersland et al. (2011).

[INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE]

Specifically, we proxy financial performance with the following variables: return on equity (ROE), which measures profitability; portfolio at risk beyond 30 days (PaR>30), which measures portfolio quality; portfolio yield (PYIELD), which is a price and revenue metric; and the ratio of operational cost to total loan portfolio (OEP), which indicates the level of operational efficiency. In line with prior research (Hermes et al. 2011; Mersland et al. 2019; Tchakoute-Tchuigoua 2010), we measure social performance by average loan size scaled by GDP per capita (ALS-GDP), number of credit clients [Cred-clients (ln)], and the percentage of female clients (Female-perc)

In our sample, MFIs control varying volumes of assets, have different levels of business experience, and operate in different geographical locations. Such systematic differences may affect performance. Accordingly, we include the following organization-specific (MFI) control variables: MFI size, which is measured by the natural logarithm of total assets (Total assets [Ln]), MFI experience (Age), regulation (Bank-regul) which indicates whether the MFI is regulated by local banking authorities and the ratio of total debt to total assets (Leverage).

In the microfinance industry, some MFIs are subject to regulation from national banking authorities while others are not. Thus, we control for regulation because past research suggests that international capital providers may prefer to invest in regulated MFIs (Wiesner and Quien 2010). We control for leverage because a high debt ratio may affect MFIs' investment behavior and performance as well as international investors' willingness to invest equity (Jensen 1986).

We also control for the business model used because the method of lending, e.g., individual lending (Indiv-loan) versus group lending, may have a performance effect (Cull et al. 2007). The legal status of MFIs, i.e., whether it is a bank or a non-bank financial institution (NBFi), is included as an additional control. While banks are licensed to provide all types of banking services, NBFIs are normally restricted in their operations and are often not allowed to provide more advanced banking services. Following

Cozarenco et al. (2016) and Cozarenco et al. (2018), we include variables that account for whether MFIs mobilize savings, and we distinguish between voluntary and mandatory savings.

Furthermore, considering the extent of macro-economic environmental variation among our 40-country sample, we include two country-specific controls: the Human Development Index (HDI) and the Economic Freedom Index (Heritage). This is to limit possible misspecifications of the MFIs' performance. Lastly, we include geographical regions and time dummies in the regressions with the latter accounting for time heterogeneity (Wooldridge 2010).

Mathematically, our model is expressed as follows:

$$\text{MFI performance} = f(\text{International ownership} + \text{control variables}) + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where:

MFI performance represents the financial and social performance of the MFI;

International ownership is represented by the proportion of shares owned by international shareholders;

Control variables represent MFI-specific and country-specific control variables as well as regional and time indicators; and ε is the error term representing the unexplained variation.

3.3 Econometric approach

We run system estimations, using seemingly unrelated regression equations (SURE) as the main method. According to its proponents, SURE is “asymptotically more efficient than single-equation least squares,” especially when the contemporaneous disturbance terms in different equations are highly correlated (Zellner and Huang 1962, p. 300). As argued by Mersland et al. (2011), the SURE method is mainly useful when we have related measures of an underlying true variable that depend upon a set of explanatory variables. The SURE method takes into account potential correlations among the dependent variables (Greene 2012, pp. 267–272). Thus, given the significant correlations between the performance variables (both financial and social; see Table 3 below), the results of the system estimations should be particularly interesting.

For all regressions, we perform a Breusch–Pagan chi-squared test to check whether the residuals in the SURE method are independent (Breusch and Pagan, 1979).

3.4 Robustness tests for endogeneity

Existing studies confirm that firms in good financial standing are more likely to attract international commercial funding (Wiesner and Quien 2010). This suggests that financial performance can determine whether international shareholders choose to invest in a particular MFI (Berger et al. 2009), as well as the

volume of investment. To address this possible endogeneity problem, we re-run all models on a subsample that consists of (1) MFIs that concurrently have international owners and are internationally initiated and (2) MFIs that have no international owners irrespective of whether they are internationally initiated or otherwise. Thus, we exclude all MFIs that are internationally owned but not internationally initiated. Naturally, we assume that the international owners have been associated with the internationally initiated MFIs from their inception. Thus, in this case, we consider our international ownership variable (Perc-shares-init) to be exogenous. As shown in Table 2, whereas 54.2% of MFIs have international owners, 34.0% are concurrently internationally owned and internationally initiated. Additionally, in an unreported analysis, we run single equation least squares where we include a one-year lag of the explanatory variable as a regressor. As argued by McKinnish (2002), the lagged explanatory variable illustrates the differential response to short- and long-term changes in the explanatory variable, and the summed coefficients of the lagged and contemporaneous variables give the long-run effect. We run the models using the dummy for international ownership (Intowner) (results are unreported).

[INSERT TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE]

4. Empirical Evidence

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the study. Before we discuss them, however, it is important to mention that we performed an analysis of possible outliers prior to conducting our investigation. The analysis revealed that the raw values of total assets and the number of clients varied greatly among MFIs. For instance, a summary of the raw data shows that the biggest MFI serves 484,000 clients while the smallest has just 10 clients. To exclude the effect of extreme observations from our results, we removed MFIs with clients below the 5th percentile and MFIs with clients above the 95th percentile from the dataset. Moreover, for the purpose of running the regressions, we took the natural logarithm of the two variables in order to further reduce any scale problems. We also winsorized ROE, operational cost ratio (OEP) and portfolio yield (PYIELD) at the top and bottom 1% to deal with outliers.

As shown in Table 2, the average ROE is 10.3%, which is slightly above the industry average of 5%-7% (including NGOs and cooperatives) as reported by Microfact (www.microfact.org). With respect to our measure of portfolio quality, we record an average PaR>30 of 5.3% against 7% in dataset with mostly NGOs used by Mersland et al. (2011), which indicates the strength of shareholder-owned firms in managing risk. The average portfolio yield is 39.8%, whereas the average operational cost ratio is around 20.3%.

The average outstanding loan per client (untabulated) stands at US\$ 1,035, with a median of US\$ 653 and a standard deviation of US\$ 1,305. This high standard deviation can be explained by differences in economic development in the various markets in which the MFIs operate. Therefore, we scale average loan size by the per capita GDP of the country where the MFI operates. Regarding the number of clients, we note that, after the outliers are removed, the average MFI has around 20,178 credit clients with a median of 10,692. The standard deviation is 23,977 credit clients, signaling that the distribution of credit clients per MFI is skewed to the right, with some MFIs serving a very high number of clients. As mentioned earlier, for the purpose of running the regressions, we take the natural logarithm of the number of credit clients variable. Continuing with the other social indicator, we see that the average MFI has 57% female clients, illustrating the female focus of microfinance.

As for the control variables, Table 2 reveals that the average MFI is about 9.5 years old and controls about US\$ 17.6 million of assets while the median MFI is endowed with about US\$ 7.9 million of assets. We use the log of assets in the regressions to get a more reasonable distribution of the variable. Interestingly, we note that the mean leverage is 0.929, indicating that on average MFIs are still far from mirroring regular banks, which traditionally have leverage levels spanning from 5 to 15 depending on the markets in which they operate. We note that 97.3% of the MFIs offer individual loans,⁴ and 73.2% of the MFIs are regulated, 90.3% are non-bank financial institutions. Finally, 35.9% of MFIs in the sample offer voluntary savings products, 30.2% collect mandatory deposits, and we observe a good global spread in the sample.

As an initial test of our research hypotheses, Table 2 presents the results of t-tests, which compare the differences in means between MFIs with international shareholders and MFIs without international shareholders in terms of the various performance indicators and control variables. MFIs with international ownership appear to have lower ROE than those without international ownership. Moreover, portfolio quality as measured by PaR>30 seems significantly better with international ownership. As for social performance, MFIs with international ownership appear to have more credit clients but are not significantly different from those without international ownership in terms of reaching out to very poor clients, as measured by average loan size scaled by GDP per capita and the percentage of female clients.

However, because there may be systematic differences between the subsamples, we await the multivariate analysis before drawing conclusions. In fact, the t-tests for the control variables suggest that such differences do exist: MFIs with international ownership are larger, less likely to be NBFIs, and situated in more developed countries, as shown in the t-tests of Table 2.

⁴ The individual loan variable is a dummy variable indicating whether the MFI offer either only individual loans or individual loans alongside group loans. About 66 percent offer individual loans only.

[INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE]

We conclude the descriptive section with a correlation analysis to check that multicollinearity between the independent test variables and the control variables is not a problem and, furthermore, to check that the performance variables are not duplicates. As shown in Table 3, there is no serious problem of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables if we use a correlation coefficient of 0.8 as the ceiling point (Kennedy 2008). We also compute variance inflation factor (VIF) to further rule out multicollinearity concerns. The highest and mean VIFs are 2.10 and 1.42, respectively. These figures are well below the upper bound of 10 (Hair et al. 2010).

4.2 Regression results

Table 4 presents the joint estimates of the dependent variables (both financial and social performance) with the percentage of shares owned by international shareholders as the explanatory variable. In the correlations of residuals reported in Table 4, the operational cost ratio is seen to be highly correlated with portfolio yield. Providing small loans is indeed costly (Mersland and Strøm 2010) and in order to meet these costs, MFIs charge high interest on their loans. Again, we find a significant negative correlation between the residuals of (the log of) the number of credit clients and average loan size. Naturally, MFIs serving smaller loans reach out to more clients. Moreover, we find a significant positive correlation between (the log of) the number of credit clients and the percentage of female clients. Overall, the Breusch–Pagan chi-squared test rejects the independence of the dependent variables. Thus, as argued by Mersland et al. (2011), the SURE method should be appropriate.

[INSERT TABLE 4 ABOUT HERE]

As shown in Table 4, ROE reduces by an average of 7.5 percentage points for every 1 percentage point increase in the percentage of shares owned by international shareholders. The lower ROE appears to be driven by operating expenses, which increases by an average are 7.6 percentage points for every one percentage point increase in the volume of international share ownership. Table 4 also shows that portfolio quality improves significantly with international ownership. Notably, high portfolio quality is resource-demanding: to select less risky clients and follow up on the clients' payback is costly (Crystal et al. 2002) and this could serve as an explanation for the higher operating costs and lower ROE in MFIs with international owners compared to MFIs without international owners. Additionally, Table 4 suggests a significant positive relationship between international ownership and portfolio yield. Given that ROE is lower with international ownership, this revenue effect appears to be lower than the cost effect of higher operating expenses for MFIs with international ownership.

We now consider the results of the social performance indicators. According to Table 4, international owners appear to increase the log of credit clients by 0.554 of a percentage point. The natural logarithm is a non-linear function, but as an example, we may note that this corresponds to an increase of about 4000-credit clients for an average-sized MFI. Moreover, international ownership is associated with a 7.9-percentage point increase in the proportion of female clients. As for the average loan size, the coefficient on the ownership variables is -0.212, which suggests that the average loan size is 21.2 percentage points lower with international ownership. Thus, as evaluated by these three significant results, international owners focus more on social performance than local owners do. This may not be overly surprising considering that the international owners in microfinance are usually impact investors (Mersland et al. 2020). It may be natural for this type of investors to be inclined towards monitoring the social outreach performance of their investee MFIs.

Of course, an institution's level of performance can attract increased investment from international shareholder (Wiesner and Quien, 2010). The causal direction between international ownership and MFI performance is thus not certain. To deal with this possible endogeneity, we check the robustness of our estimates by re-running our models on a sub-sample that consist of internationally initiated MFIs that have international owners and MFIs that have no international owners irrespective of whether they are internationally initiated or not. As noted earlier, this sub-sample excludes all locally initiated MFIs having international owners at the time of data collection. Here, we assume that the international owner and the initiator have been associated with the MFI from its inception. Thus, the international ownership variable is assumed to be exogenous. Table 5 presents the SURE estimates of MFI performance on the percentage of shares owned by international shareholders in MFIs that are initiated by an international organization (Perc-shares-init) and the set of control variables. The results reported in Table 5 confirm those reported in Tables 4. Thus, we maintain our conclusion that the cost effect of international ownership dominates the revenue effect, leading to low profitability. Furthermore, the results also affirm that international ownership supports greater social outreach.

[INSERT TABLE 5 ABOUT HERE]

We run several additional robustness checks. First, whether an MFI collects deposits could potentially influence its financial performance since deposit mobilization may affect its cost and capital structures. We accounted for this effect in the baseline models by including binary variables for voluntary and mandatory savings. In unreported regressions, we add the volume of mobilized savings as a control. The results remain unchanged.

Second, as suggested in the literature, international investors often require stricter risk-monitoring

mechanisms aimed at safeguarding their investment (García-Herrero and Santabárbara, 2008). Such mechanisms sometimes involve considerable investments in human resources and other cost-driving initiatives. Thus, in untabulated regressions we tested and found that MFIs with international shareholders indeed have significantly higher personnel costs than MFIs without international shareholders. In order to ensure loan quality, international owners appear to influence MFIs to hire more experienced and/or more costly staff. The higher personnel costs could also arise from an increased focus on outreach or on social performance in general.

Third, as indicated by McKinnish (2002), including the lagged explanatory variable as a regressor produces the differential response to the short- and long-term changes in the explanatory variable. Alternatively, the summed coefficients of the lagged and contemporaneous variables can be seen as giving an indication of the long-run effect. In order to reduce model misspecification resulting from omission of the lagged explanatory variable, we run single equation least squares (unreported) where we include a one-year lag of the international ownership variable as a regressor (see also Heckman and Hotz, 1989). The results generally show that, the one-year lag values have a similar relationship with performance as the contemporaneous international ownership variable has with it. Interestingly, in line with McKinnish's (2002) argument, we also observe that the summed coefficients of international ownership and the one-year lagged values of international ownership produce an effect that is equivalent to the main results reported earlier.

5. Discussion

This study investigates how international ownership affects the financial and social performance of social enterprises, using data from MFIs. Though we recognize the possible negative performance impact of international ownership due to liability of foreignness, we generally expected an overall positive performance impact of international ownership given that international owners have clearly defined fiduciary duties and rights to appropriate residual earnings (Hansmann 1996). Thus, drawing on agency theory and resource-based theory, we hypothesized a positive influence of international ownership on financial performance.

Regarding social performance, the literature is less ambiguous, and we hypothesized a positive influence of international ownership on social performance. We concluded the hypothesis development section with a discussion of previous microfinance research suggesting that there is often a trade-off between financial and social performance.

We believe that the key to understanding and explaining the empirical findings of this study lies in interpreting the results in light of this possible trade-off between financial and social objectives. Though we considered it natural to base our hypotheses on conventional theories like agency theory and resource-

based theory as well as from the perspective of liability of foreignness, we now suggest that such theories need to be accompanied by a trade-off theory when studying influence of international equity investors. Thus, we suggest that our empirical findings are a first step toward a better understanding of the internationalization process of firms that combine both financial and social logics.

Specifically, we believe that the starting point for interpreting our results should be the documented evidence on MFIs' social performance. International ownership appears to lead to a higher number of credit clients, smaller loan amounts, and increased outreach to female clients. Therefore, international equity investors in the microfinance industry seem to have a deliberate and clear intention of improving the social performance of MFIs, that is, fighting poverty and fostering financial inclusion. This finding fits well with a new trend suggesting that a proportion of modern investors are socially concerned investors who tend to be more focused on social returns than on mere financial payoff (Chmelik et al. 2016; Mersland et al. 2020).

However, the social returns do come at a cost: improved social performance is associated with higher operating expenses, which lead to lower ROE. Notably, the contention of our study that international investors in microfinance are more "social" can also be reversed, i.e., local investors seem to be more concerned with financial performance than with social performance, compared to their international counterparts.

In the social enterprise context, the results are natural. For instance, Weerawardena and Mort (2006, p. 22) find social enterprises to be "deeply rooted" in their social missions. The social mission is thus a key defining element of social enterprises and a major source of their legitimacy (Peredo and McLean 2006; Sunduramurthy et al. 2016). Several scholars regard the offer of small loans, especially to women, as the basic pillar of the modern MFI (Armendáriz and Morduch 2010). But reaching more vulnerable clients is associated with higher costs (Mersland and Strøm 2010). For instance, the administrative workload associated with a small loan is often almost as large as that associated with a bigger loan. In fact, the workload may actually be larger for small loans: if clients that receive small loans are particularly vulnerable, say disabled or illiterate, additional or extraordinary client assistance might be needed (Beisland and Mersland 2017). Moreover, reaching out to more clients, inclusive of new sectors of clients that have not previously been involved with a formal MFI, may obviously also generate extra costs. Overall, investors that want to contribute to poverty eradication may have to give up some financial returns (Cull et al. 2007; Mersland et al. 2020).

That said, it is important to remember that there is not necessarily a conflict between profit maximization and the fight against poverty. Large commercial banks have entered the microfinance market and, by reaching people that previously had no access to financial services, have shown that profit maximization can go hand in hand with the servicing of vulnerable clients. Some field observers argue

that profit orientation propels MFIs to operate in an efficient manner, which in turn enables them to expand their outreach to poorer clients (Mersland and Strøm 2010).

However, if investors deliberately target particularly vulnerable groups of people who would not otherwise have gained access to (commercial) microfinance services, there may be further costs involved. This study shows that international investors in the microfinance industry are willing to bear such extra costs (Briere and Szafarz 2015; Mersland et al. 2011), since they are mostly pro-social investors. The clue to understanding the results of our study probably lies in realizing that such investors do not have a one-dimensional utility function based on financial returns only. Rather, the utility function also includes a social return dimension: social investors require something more than mere profit maximization for their payoff/return to be optimized (Briere and Szafarz 2015; Chmelik et al. 2016).

Though our findings are largely in line with our theoretical expectations, there are some results that may appear paradoxical. First, portfolio quality is higher in MFIs with international ownership than in their locally owned counterparts. Higher portfolio quality is generally associated with a stricter client-screening process, a tougher money collection method, or both (Crystal et al. 2002). Such banking practices may harm the poor and vulnerable. If international shareholders care more about social performance in the form of poverty eradication, why do they focus so much on portfolio quality? The explanation may lie in the history of microfinance. After all, modern microfinance developed stronger repayment incentives (group loans, step-wise loans, etc.) in the 1970s and 1980s as a response to very high default rates in rural and agricultural lending programs sponsored by Western donors (Hulme and Mosley 1996; Sievers and Vandenberg 2007). Thus, international investors today do not want to repeat historical mistakes.

Moreover, the fact that internationally owned MFIs are less embedded in the local political and economic environment may put them at a disadvantage when it comes to risk assessment and how to handle a distressed situation for the MFI (Lensink et al. 2008). International investors are simply less familiar with the business and regulatory environments of their new markets. Thus, there are logical reasons why internationally owned MFIs should keep their risk low (García-Herrero and Santabárbara 2008).

We conclude this section by noting some interesting results on MFI age. More microfinance experience appears to be associated with improved financial performance as measured by ROE and operating cost. This is hardly surprising, and the most obvious explanation is learning effects (Williams and Nguyen 2005). However, at the same time, experience appears to be associated also with improved social performance: both lower average loan size and more credit clients. Thus, a promising direction for future research is to study how experience may help balance the trade-off between financial and social logics in social enterprises.

6. Conclusions and Implications

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of international ownership on the social and financial performance of social enterprises, using evidence from the global microfinance industry. Research on the impact of international ownership on regular enterprises suggests that international owners can enhance the financial performance of investee companies through improved governance, knowledge transfer and networking (Gulamhussen and Guerreiro, 2009; Musteen et al. 2010). Within the domain of social enterprises, however, only a few empirical studies have investigated the effect of internationalization on firm performance (Chmelik et al. 2016; Mersland et al. 2011), and we are unaware of any empirical study addressing the effect of international ownership on MFI performance. For this reason, we consider our study pioneering and particularly important for the social enterprise and microfinance literature. Our analysis of MFIs suggests that international owners are more concerned than local owners about the social performance of the enterprises in which they invest. Our results on financial performance are mixed. While internationally owned MFIs have better portfolio quality and higher portfolio yield, they incur higher operating cost and show lower overall financial performance in terms of ROE. It appears that international owners of MFIs are more willing to trade off better financial performance for better social performance.

We acknowledge that our findings do not fit well with conventional hypotheses based on agency theory, resource-based theory, or the liability of foreignness perspective. The reason, in our view, is that conventional ownership theories are developed based on regular profit maximizing firms. The contrary, socially oriented owners in firms with dual objectives have more complex utility functions than owners of regular firms. Importantly, our data show that the social performance dimension is more important to international owners of MFIs than to local owners.

From an academic perspective, we believe researchers should continue developing theories for firms with conflicting objectives. Firms and investors combining financial and social objectives are on the rise (Chmelik et al. 2016; Mersland et al. 2020) and current ownership theory (or in more general terms governance theory) does not appear to provide a good description of the reality of such firms (Holmstrom and Milgrom 1991). For example, they do not address how the multidimensional utility function might affect the governance and financing of a social enterprise.

We also believe that our study has important practical implications. One is obvious: socially concerned MFIs seeking to raise new capital should approach international sources. There is also a macro-perspective to this line of reasoning: policy makers concerned about the social performance of MFIs should facilitate access to international equity for these entities. This can have direct consequences for the regulations that MFIs face in many countries where international ownership is depressed compared to local ownership (Abeysekera et al. 2014).

In addition, our study poses a big question for future research: why are national investors not as concerned with social performance as international investors? Are international actors and owners needed to “police” the social component of microfinance? Or, alternatively, does international ownership restrain a much-needed evolution toward an increased market and commercial focus in microfinance? After all, 2.3 billion people in the world remain unserved or underserved in emerging markets (ResponsAbility 2017). For them it may be unimportant whether they are reached by commercial or social bankers. Indeed, this is a question researchers should investigate: does the type of ownership and the owners’ profit orientation really matter to those in need of services?

Finally, if MFIs need to raise the price of microcredit (increase portfolio yield) to be able to reach more vulnerable clients, as documented in this paper, there is not only a conflict between financial and social performance, but also a conflict between two social performance metrics: the price of the service and the access to the service (Schreiner 2002). This is another trade-off that should be addressed in future research.

References

- Abeyssekera, S., Oguzoglu, U., & Tam Le, T. (2014). Sustainability and mission drift: Do microfinance institutions in Vietnam reach the poor? In R. Mersland & R.Ø. Strøm (eds.), *Microfinance Institutions: Financial and Social Performance* (pp. 99–118). Berlin: Springer.
- Ackerman, J. (2004). Co-governance for accountability: Beyond “exit” and “voice.” *World Development*, 32(3), 447–463.
- Armendáriz, B., & Morduch, J. (2010). *The Economics of Microfinance*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Ausburg, B., & Fouillet, C. (2010). Profit empowerment: The microfinance institution’s mission drift. *Perspectives on Global Development and Technology*, 9, 327–355.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Battilana, J., & Dorado, S. (2010). Building sustainable hybrid organizations: The case of commercial microfinance organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(6), 1419–1440.
- Beisland, L.A. & Mersland, R., (2017), "Exploring Microfinance Clients with Disabilities: A Case Study of an Ecuadorian Microbank". *Journal of Development Studies*. Vol. 53(11), pp. 1929–1943.
- Berger, A. N., Clarke, G. R., Cull, R., Klapper, L., & Udell, G. F. (2005). Corporate governance and bank performance: A joint analysis of the static, selection, and dynamic effects of domestic, foreign, and state ownership. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(8), 2179–2221.
- Berger, A. N., Hasan, I., & Zhou, M. (2009). Bank ownership and efficiency in China: What will happen in the world’s largest nation? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 33(1), 113–130.
- Bharath, S. T., Jayaraman, S., & Nagar, V. (2013). Exit as governance: An empirical analysis. *The Journal of Finance*, 68(6), 2515–2547.
- Bonin, J. P., Hasan, I., & Wachtel, P. (2005). Bank performance, efficiency and ownership in transition countries. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(1), 31–53.
- Breusch, T. S., & Pagan, A. R. (1979). A simple test for heteroscedasticity and random coefficient variation. *Econometrica*, 47(5), 1287–1294.
- Briere, M., & Szafarz, A. (2015). Does commercial microfinance belong to the financial sector? Lessons from the stock market. *World Development*, 67, 110–125.

- Bruton, G. D., Filatotchev, I., Chahine, S., & Wright, M. (2010). Governance, ownership structure, and performance of IPO firms: The impact of different types of private equity investors and institutional environments. *Strategic Management Journal*, 31(5), 491–509.
- Buckley, P. J., & Casson, M. C. (1998). Analyzing foreign market entry strategies: Extending the internalization approach. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 29(3), 539–561.
- Chmelik, E., Musteen, M., & Ahsan, M. (2016) Measures of performance in the context of international social ventures: An exploratory study. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 7(1), 74–100.
- Choi, S., & Hasan, I. (2005). Ownership, governance, and bank performance: Korean experience. *Financial Markets, Institutions & Instruments*, 14(4), 215–242.
- Cobb, J. A., Wry, T., & Zhao, E. Y. (2016). Funding financial inclusion: Institutional logics and the contextual contingency of funding for microfinance organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 59(6), 2103–2131.
- Cozarenco, A., Hartarska, V., & Szafarz, A. (2018). Too many cooks spoil the broth: The conflicting impacts of subsidies and deposits on the cost-efficiency of microfinance institutions. *Available at SSRN 3295173*.
- Cozarenco, A., Hudon, M., & Szafarz, A. (2016). What type of microfinance institutions supply savings products? *Economics Letters*, 140, 57–59.
- Cozarenco, A., & Szafarz, A. (2014). Microcredit in developed countries: unexpected consequences of loan ceilings. *Brussels: CEB Working Paper*, (14/015).
- Crystal, J. S., Dages, B. G., & Goldberg, L. S. (2002). Has foreign bank entry led to sounder banks in Latin America? *Current Issues in Economics and Finance*, 8(1), 1–6.
- Cull, R., Demigüç-Kunt, A., & Morduch, J. (2007). Financial performance and outreach: A global analysis of leading microbanks. *The Economic Journal*, 117, 107–133.
- D’Espallier, B., Goedecke, J., Hudon, M., & Mersland, R. (2017). From NGOs to banks: Does institutional transformation alter the business model of microfinance institutions? *World Development* 89, 19–33
- Dobrev, S. D., Kim, T.-Y., & Carroll, G. R. (2003). Shifting gears, shifting niches: Organizational inertia and change in the evolution of the U.S. automobile industry, 1885–1981. *Organization Science*, 14, 264–282.
- Doidge, C., Karolyi, G. A., & Stulz, R. M. (2007). Why do countries matter so much for corporate governance? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 86(1), 1–39.
- Dorflleitner, G., Röhe, M., & Renier, N. (2017). The access of microfinance institutions to debt capital: An empirical investigation of microfinance investment vehicles. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 65, 1–15.
- Dunning, J. H. (2000). The eclectic paradigm as an envelope for economic and business theories of MNE activity. *International Business Review*, 9, 163–190.
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *The Journal of Law & Economics*, 26(2), 301–325.
- García-Herrero, A., & Santabábara, D. (2008). Is the Chinese banking system benefiting from foreign investors? BBVA Working Paper No. 0804.
- Greene, W. H. (2012). *Econometric Analysis* (7th ed.). New York: Prentice Hall.
- Gulamhussen, M. A., & Guerreiro, L. (2009). The influence of foreign equity and board membership on corporate strategy and internal cost management in Portuguese banks. *Management Accounting Research*, 20(1), 6–17.
- Hair, J. F. J., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Hansmann, H. (1996). *The Ownership of Enterprise*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Hartarska, V. (2005). Governance and performance of microfinance institutions in Central and Eastern Europe and the newly independent states. *World Development*, 33(10), 1627–1643.
- Hearn, B., Piesse, J., & Strange, R. (2010). Market liquidity and stock size premia in emerging

- financial markets: The implications for foreign investment. *International Business Review*, 19(5), 489–501.
- Heckman, J. J., & Hotz, V. J. (1989). Choosing among alternative non-experimental methods for estimating the impact of social programs: The case of manpower training. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 84(408), 862–874.
- Hermes, N., Lensink, R., & Meesters, A. (2011). Outreach and efficiency of microfinance institutions. *World Development*, 39(6), 938–948.
- Heugens, P. P., Van Essen, M., & van Oosterhout, J. H. (2009). Meta-analyzing ownership concentration and firm performance in Asia: Towards a more fine-grained understanding. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 26(3), 481–512.
- Holmstrom, B., & Milgrom, P. (1991). Multitask principal-agent analyses: Incentive contracts, asset ownership, and job design. *Journal of Law, Economics & Organization*, 7, 24–52.
- Hudon, M., & Traca, D. (2011). On the efficiency effects of subsidies in microfinance: An empirical inquiry. *World Development*, 39, 966–973.
- Hulme, D., & Mosley, P. (1996). *Finance against Poverty*. London: Routledge.
- Hymer, S. H. (1976). *The International Operations of National Firms: A Study of Direct Foreign Investment* (Vol. 14, pp. 139–155). Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Jensen, M. C. (1986). Agency costs of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers. *The American Economic Review*, 76(2), 323–329.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.
- Kennedy, P. (2008). *A Guide to Econometrics* (6th ed.). Malden, MA: Blackwell Publishing.
- Kent, D., & Dacin, M. T. (2013). Bankers at the gate: Microfinance and the high cost of borrowed logics. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(6), 759–773.
- Lahaye, E. (2016). Leveraging equity investments to build inclusive financial markets. The World Bank, Focus Note 104.
- Ledgerwood, J. (2013). Institutional providers. In J. Ledgerwood, J. Earne, & C.J. Nelson, C. J. (eds.), *The new Microfinance Handbook: A Financial Market System Perspective* (pp. 171–196). Washington, D. C. The World Bank.
- Lensink, R., Meesters, A., & Naaborg, I. (2008). Bank efficiency and foreign ownership: Do good institutions matter? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 32(5), 834–844.
- Lin, X., & Zhang, Y. (2009). Bank ownership reform and bank performance in China. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 33(1), 20–29.
- Lu, J. W., & Beamish, P. W. (2004). International diversification and firm performance: The S-curve hypothesis. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(4), 598–609.
- Lützenkirchen, C., & Weistroffer, C. (2012). *Microfinance in evolution: An industry between crisis and advancement*. Frankfurt am Main: Deutsche Bank Research.
- Mair, J., & Marti, I. (2006). Social entrepreneurship research: A source of explanation, prediction, and delight. *Journal of World Business*, 41(1), 36–44.
- Manolova, T. S., Manev, I. M., & Gyoshev, B. S. (2010). In good company: The role of personal and inter-firm networks for new-venture internationalization in a transition economy. *Journal of World Business*, 45(3), 257–265.
- Masulis, R. W., Wang, C., & Xie, F. (2012). Globalizing the boardroom: The effects of foreign directors on corporate governance and firm performance. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 53(3), 527–554.
- McKinnish, T. G. (2002). Interpreting lagged effects of the independent variable: How does the local economy affect welfare caseloads? Retrieved 13.07.18 from [http:// stripe.colorado.edu](http://stripe.colorado.edu)
- Mersland, R. (2009). The cost of ownership in microfinance organizations. *World Development*, 37(2), 469–478.

- Mersland, R., Nyarko, S. A., & Sirisena, A. B. (2020). A hybrid approach to international market selection: The case of impact investing organizations. *International Business Review*, 29(1), 101624.
- Mersland, R., Nyarko, S. A., & Szafarz, A. (2019). Do social enterprises walk the talk? Assessing microfinance performances with mission statements. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 11, e00117.
- Mersland, R., Randøy, T., & Strøm, R. Ø. (2011). The impact of international influence on microbanks' performance: A global survey. *International Business Review*, 20 (2), 163–176.
- Mersland, R., & Strøm, R. Ø. (2010). Microfinance mission drift? *World Development*, 38(1), 28–36.
- Mersland, R., & Strøm, R. Ø. (2009). Performance and governance in microfinance institutions. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 33(4), 662–669.
- Mersland, R., & Urgeghe, L. (2013). International debt financing and performance of microfinance institutions. *Strategic Change*, 22(1–2), 17–29.
- Miller, S. R., & Parkhe, A. (2002). Is there a liability of foreignness in global banking? An empirical test of banks' X-efficiency. *Strategic Management Journal*, 23(1), 55–75.
- Mori, N., Golesorkhi, S., Randøy, T., & Hermes, N. (2015). Board composition and outreach performance of microfinance institutions: Evidence from East Africa. *Strategic Change*, 24(1), 99–113.
- Musteen, M., Francis, J., & Datta, D. K. (2010). The influence of international networks on internationalization speed and performance: A study of Czech SMEs. *Journal of World Business*, 45(3), 197–205.
- Oxelheim, L., & Randøy, T. (2003). The impact of foreign board membership on firm value. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 27(12), 2369–2392.
- Oxelheim, L., Randøy, T., & Stonehill, A. (2001). On the treatment of finance-specific factors within the OLI paradigm. *International Business Review*, 10(4), 381–398.
- Peng, M. W., Wang, D. Y. L., & Jiang, Y. (2008). An institution-based view of international business strategy: A focus on emerging economies. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 39(5), 920–936.
- Peredo, A. M., & McLean, M. (2006). Social entrepreneurship: A critical review of the concept. *Journal of World Business*, 41(1), 56–65.
- Pedrini, M., Bramanti, V., Minciullo, M., & Ferri, L. M. (2016). Rethinking microfinance for developed countries. *Journal of International Development*, 28(2), 281–302.
- Randøy, T., Oxelheim, L., & Stonehill, A. (2001). Corporate financial strategies for global competitiveness. *European Management Journal*, 19(6), 659–669.
- Reille, X., Forster, S., & Rozas, D. (2011). Foreign capital investment in microfinance: Reassessing financial and social returns. The World Bank, Focus Note 71.
- ResponsAbility (2017). Micro and SME Finance market outlook. Retrieved on 07.07.2017 from <https://www.responsability.com/en/micro-and-sme-finance-market-outlook>
- Rugman, A. M., Verbeke, A., & Nguyen, Q. T. (2011). Fifty years of international business theory and beyond. *Management International Review*, 51(6), 755–786.
- Ruigrok, W., & Wagner, H. (2003). Internationalization and performance: An organizational learning perspective. *Management International Review*, 43(1), 63–84.
- Ruigrok, W., Amann, W., & Wagner, H. (2003). The Internationalization-Performance Relationship at Swiss Firms: A Test of the S-Shape and Extreme Degrees of Internationalization. *Management International Review*, 47(3), 349–368.
- Schreiner, M. (2002). Aspects of outreach: A framework for discussion of the social benefits of microfinance. *Journal of International Development*, 14, 591–603.
- Servin, R., Lensink, R., & Van den Berg, M. (2012). Ownership and technical efficiency of microfinance institutions: Empirical evidence from Latin America. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 36(7), 2136–2144.

- Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *The Journal of Finance*, 52(2), 737–783.
- Sievers, M., & Vandenberg, P. (2007). Synergies through linkages: Who benefits from linking micro-finance and business development services? *World Development*, 35(8), 1341–1358.
- Soursourian, M., Dashi, E., & Dokle, E. (2015). Current trends in international funding for financial inclusion. Consultative Group to Assist the Poor. Retrieved on 10.01.2016 from www.cgap.org
- Strange, R., Filatotchev, I., Buck, T., & Wright, M. (2009). Corporate governance and international business. *Management International Review*, 49(4), 395–407.
- Sunduramurthy, C., Zheng, C., Musteen, M., Francis, J., & Rhyne, L. (2016). Doing more with less, systematically? Bricolage and ingenieuring in successful social ventures. *Journal of World Business*, 51(5), 855–870.
- Tchakoute-Tchuigoua, H. (2010). Is there a difference in performance by the legal status of microfinance institutions? *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 50(4), 436–442.
- Unite, A. A., & Sullivan, M. J. (2003). The effect of foreign entry and ownership structure on the Philippine domestic banking market. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 27(12), 2323–2345.
- Weerawardena, J., & Mort, G. S. (2006). Investigating social entrepreneurship: A multidimensional model. *Journal of World Business*, 41(1), 21–35.
- Wiesner, S., & Quien, D. (2010). Can “bad” microfinance practices be the consequence of too much funding chasing too few microfinance institutions? ADA Discussion Paper 2.
- Williams, J., & Nguyen, N. (2005). Financial liberalization, crisis, and restructuring: A comparative study of bank performance and bank governance in South East Asia. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 29(8), 2119–2154.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2010). *Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data* (2nd ed.). Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Yoshikawa, T., & Phan, P. H. (2001). Alternative corporate governance systems in Japanese firms: Implications for a shift to stockholder-centered corporate governance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 18(2), 183–205.
- Yoshikawa, T., & Phan, P. H. (2003). The performance implications of ownership-driven governance reform. *European Management Journal*, 21(6), 698–706.
- Zaheer, S., & Mosakowski, E. (1997). The dynamics of the liability of foreignness: A global study of survival in financial services. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(6), 439–463.
- Zellner, A., & Huang, D. S. (1962). Further properties of efficient estimators for seemingly unrelated regression equations. *International Economic Review*, 3(3), 300–313.

Table 1: Explanation of Variables Used in the Study

Variables	Explanation	Hypotheses
<i>Dependent Variables</i>		
<i>Financial Performance</i>		
ROE	Profitability measure: net income divided by average total owners' equity	+
OEP	Total operating expenses divided by total loan portfolio	-
PYIELD	Interest income from portfolio divided by average gross portfolio	+
PAR>30	Proportion of loan portfolio that is 30 days or more overdue	-
<i>Social performance</i>		
ALS-GDP	Average outstanding loan amount as percentage of GDP per capita	+
Cred-clients (ln)	Natural logarithm of the total number of credit clients	+
Female-perc	Percentage of female clients	+
<i>Independent variables</i>		
Intowner	Whether the MFI has an international shareholder: Yes = 1, No = 0	
Perc-shares	Percentage of shares owned by international shareholders	
Perc-shares-init	Percentage of shares owned by international shareholders in internationally initiated MFIs. Used only in robustness checks	
<i>MFI-specific controls</i>		
Total assets (ln)	Natural logarithm of end-of-period total assets	
Age	Years since the MFI started microfinance operations	
Leverage	Ratio of total debt including deposits to total assets	
Bank-regul	Whether the MFI is regulated by banking authorities: Yes = 1, No = 0	
Indiv-loan	Whether the MFI gives individual loans: Yes = 1, No = 0	
NBFI	Whether the MFI is a non-bank financial institution: Yes = 1, No = 0	
Voluntary-sav	Whether the MFI offers voluntary savings product to clients: Yes = 1, No = 0	
Mandatory-sav	Whether the MFI requires mandatory savings from clients: Yes = 1, No = 0	
<i>Country/regional controls</i>		
HDI	Human Development Index of the country where the MFI is located	
Heritage	Economic Freedom Index of country as reported by the Heritage Foundation	
Region ECS	Countries from Eastern Europe and Central Asia	
Region EAS	Countries from East Asia and the Pacific	
Region SAS	Countries from South Asia	
Region LCN	Countries from Latin America and the Caribbean	
Region MEA	Countries from the Middle East and North Africa	
Region SSF	Countries from Sub-Saharan Africa	

Note: Regional classifications and acronyms are those employed by the World Bank.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and t-test

Variables	Obs.	Mean (Combined)	Median	Std. dev.	Min	Max	Mean Intowner = 1	Mean Intowner = 0	Std. error difference	t-statistic
<i>Main Independent</i>										
Intowner	526	0.542	1	0.499	0	1				
Perc-shares	526	0.370	0.168	0.407	0	1				
Perc-shares-init	416	0.305	0	0.419	0	1				
<i>Performance variables</i>										
ROE	526	0.103	0.114	0.218	-0.990	0.581	0.083	0.125	0.019	2.215**
OEP	526	0.203	0.169	0.112	0.034	0.700	0.209	0.192	0.010	1.753*
PYIELD	526	0.398	0.365	0.170	0.140	1.013	0.398	0.397	0.015	0.096
PAR>30	526	0.053	0.034	0.062	0.002	0.390	0.043	0.064	0.005	3.928***
ALS-GDP	526	0.622	0.368	0.777	0.010	5.990	0.615	0.630	0.068	0.223
Credit clients	526	20178	10692	23977	1015	145527	23300	16485	2079.031	3.278***
Cred-clients (ln)	526	9.283	9.277	1.170	6.923	11.888	9.412	9.130	0.102	2.769***
Female-perc	526	0.570	0.573	0.170	0.180	1	0.578	0.561	0.015	1.185
<i>Control variables</i>										
Total assets ('000)	526	17600.000	7875.587	26500.000	45.636	171000.000	19600.000	15300.000	2317.323	1.863*
Total assets (ln)	526	15.889	15.879	1.301	10.728	18.957	16.083	15.660	0.112	3.767***
Age	526	9.477	9	5.231	0	35	9.582	9.353	0.458	0.502
Indiv-loan	526	0.973	1	0.161	0	1	0.982	0.963	0.014	1.406
Leverage	526	0.929	0.662	3.944	0.013	59.661	1.046	0.791	0.345	0.739
Bank-regul	526	0.732	1	0.443	0	1	0.705	0.763	0.039	1.502
NBFI	526	0.903	1	0.296	0	1	0.881	0.929	0.026	1.886*
Voluntary-sav	526	0.359	0	0.480	0	1	0.337	0.386	0.042	1.168
Mandatory-sav	526	0.302	0	0.460	0	1	0.270	0.340	0.040	1.745*
HDI	526	0.598	0.652	0.143	0.206	0.792	0.602	0.594	0.013	0.591
Heritage	526	55.969	55.18	5.686	40.600	71.360	56.744	55.052	0.493	3.436***
Region ECS	526	0.215	0	0.411	0	1				
Region EAS	526	0.137	0	0.344	0	1				
Region SAS	526	0.006	0	0.075	0	1				
Region LCN	526	0.338	0	0.474	0	1				
Region MEA	526	0.032	0	0.177	0	1				
Region SSF	526	0.272	0	0.445	0	1				

*, **, *** indicate significance levels of 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Table 3: Correlation matrix

	No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
ROE	1	1.000								
OEP	2	-0.212	1.000							
PYIELD	3	0.053	0.747	1.000						
PaR >30	4	-0.225	-0.191	-0.196	1.000					
ALS-GDP	5	-0.071	-0.208	-0.200	0.048	1.000				
Cred-clients (ln)	6	0.162	-0.089	0.009	-0.141	-0.105	1.000			
Female-perc	7	0.006	0.223	0.212	-0.082	-0.179	0.240	1.000		
Perc-shares	8	-0.139	0.121	0.006	-0.194	0.020	0.026	-0.011	1.000	
Total assets (ln)	9	0.175	-0.346	-0.182	0.014	0.039	0.622	-0.104	0.079	1.000
Age	10	0.142	-0.188	-0.275	0.076	-0.040	0.402	-0.003	0.013	0.421
Indiv-loan	11	-0.008	0.007	-0.008	0.076	0.030	0.057	-0.055	0.082	0.166
Leverage	12	0.030	-0.007	-0.016	-0.063	-0.001	0.053	0.122	0.066	-0.212
Bank-regul	13	0.053	-0.223	-0.169	0.091	0.186	0.160	-0.198	-0.066	0.264
NBFI	14	0.054	0.020	-0.028	-0.004	-0.447	-0.264	0.063	-0.051	-0.287
Voluntary-sav	15	-0.018	-0.145	-0.037	0.218	0.246	0.374	0.031	-0.100	0.184
Mandatory-sav	16	-0.182	0.054	-0.026	0.102	0.108	0.239	0.265	-0.057	-0.220
HDI	17	0.250	-0.008	0.109	-0.030	-0.360	-0.214	-0.099	0.035	0.244
Heritage	18	-0.032	0.237	0.145	-0.136	-0.063	-0.011	0.178	0.088	-0.140

	No.	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Age	10	1.000								
Indiv-loan	11	0.065	1.000							
Leverage	12	0.064	0.010	1.000						
Bank-regul	13	0.073	-0.020	0.036	1.000					
NBFI	14	-0.257	-0.054	0.041	-0.169	1.000				
Voluntary-sav	15	0.145	0.075	0.028	0.310	-0.330	1.000			
Mandatory-sav	16	0.106	-0.123	0.064	0.006	-0.022	0.301	1.000		
HDI	17	-0.033	0.143	-0.029	-0.069	0.230	-0.387	-0.636	1.000	
Heritage	18	-0.059	0.044	0.037	-0.275	-0.031	-0.070	-0.065	-0.012	1.000

Table 3 presents the pairwise correlation of international ownership variables and the set of financial and social performance indicators. We also include the set of institutional control variables. The 5% and 1% significance levels are represented in bold and bold italics, respectively.

Table 4: The percentage of shares held by international owners and microfinance performance: Joint estimates of financial and social performance

VARIABLES	ROE (1)	OEP (2)	PYIELD (3)	PAR>30 (4)	ALS-GDP (5)	Cred-clients (ln) (6)	Female-perc (7)
Perc-shares	-0.075*** (0.024)	0.076*** (0.011)	0.063*** (0.018)	-0.023*** (0.007)	-0.212*** (0.077)	0.554*** (0.111)	0.079*** (0.016)
Total assets (ln)	-0.002 (0.009)	-0.054*** (0.004)	-0.055*** (0.007)	0.004 (0.002)	0.183*** (0.028)	⁵	-0.022*** (0.006)
Age	0.008*** (0.002)	-0.002** (0.001)	-0.009*** (0.002)	0.001 (0.001)	-0.035*** (0.006)	0.060*** (0.009)	-0.002* (0.001)
Indiv-loan	-0.079 (0.055)	0.021 (0.026)	-0.026 (0.041)	0.025 (0.015)	0.306* (0.176)	-0.003 (0.258)	-0.102*** (0.036)
Leverage	0.001 (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.017** (0.007)	0.004 (0.010)	0.002 (0.002)
Bank-regul	-0.019 (0.024)	-0.002 (0.011)	-0.031* (0.018)	0.007 (0.007)	-0.022 (0.076)	0.366*** (0.109)	-0.027* (0.016)
NBFI	0.003 (0.035)	-0.090*** (0.016)	-0.165*** (0.026)	0.024** (0.010)	-0.901*** (0.111)	-0.391** (0.160)	-0.047** (0.023)
Voluntary-sav	0.040* (0.023)	-0.005 (0.011)	0.034** (0.017)	0.025*** (0.006)	0.024 (0.073)	0.482*** (0.105)	0.013 (0.015)
Mandatory-sav	-0.028 (0.027)	0.027** (0.012)	0.045** (0.020)	0.006 (0.008)	-0.000 (0.086)	0.300** (0.125)	0.118*** (0.017)
HDI	-0.252* (0.145)	0.183*** (0.068)	0.464*** (0.109)	0.076* (0.041)	-2.906*** (0.465)	-0.437 (0.672)	-0.120 (0.094)
Heritage	-0.002 (0.002)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.002* (0.001)	-0.001 (0.000)	-0.008 (0.005)	0.013* (0.008)	0.004*** (0.001)
Constant	0.221 (0.245)	0.860*** (0.115)	1.059*** (0.184)	-0.116* (0.069)	1.261 (0.782)	7.550*** (1.015)	1.213*** (0.160)
Region dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Model statistics							
Observations	526	526	526	526	526	526	526
R-squared	0.212	0.333	0.261	0.222	0.340	0.401	0.446
χ^2 statistic	145.14	346.83	248.77	167.68	346.33	351.81	446.83
Prob > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Correlation of residuals							
	ROE	OEP	PYIELD	PAR>30	ALS-GDP	Cred-clients (ln)	Female-perc
ROE	1.000						
OEP	-0.100	1.000					
PYIELD	0.169	0.726	1.000				
PAR>30	-0.274	-0.202	-0.249	1.000			
ALS-GDP	0.032	-0.220	-0.223	0.069	1.000		
Cred-clients (ln)	0.176	0.191	0.227	-0.269	-0.313	1.000	
Female-perc	0.026	0.118	0.182	-0.019	-0.107	0.161	1.000
Breusch-Pagan Chi square = 642.772			P-value = 0.000				

Table 4 presents the joint estimates of microfinance performance on the percentage of shares held by international owners (*Perc-shares*) and the set control variables using seemingly unrelated regression equations (SURE). (All variables are defined in Table 1.) For financial performance, *ROE* is the return on equity, *OEP* is the ratio of total operational expenses

⁵ Largely, the total assets of the MFI explain the variation in the total number of credit clients. Thus, to avoid an exaggerated R-square, we exclude this variable in all regressions where the log of credit clients [Cred-clients (ln)] is the dependent variable.

to total assets, *PYIELD* represents the ratio of interest income over total loan portfolio, and *PAR>30* represents the share of the MFI loan portfolio that is over 30 days in arrears. As a proxy for social performance, *ALS-GDP* is the average loan size (scaled by GDP per capita), *Cred-clients (ln)* represents the log of the total number of credit clients and *Female-perc* is the percentage of female clients. Regressors are defined in Table 1. ***, **, and * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. Standard errors appear in parentheses.

Table 5: The effect of international ownership in internationally initiated MFIs: Joint estimates of financial and social performance

VARIABLES	ROE (1)	OEP (2)	PYIELD (3)	PAR>30 (4)	ALS-GDP (5)	Cred-clients (ln) (6)	Female-perc (7)
Perc-shares-init	-0.102*** (0.027)	0.087*** (0.014)	0.062*** (0.021)	-0.022*** (0.008)	-0.220** (0.091)	0.556*** (0.134)	0.070*** (0.019)
Total assets (ln)	-0.008 (0.009)	-0.054*** (0.005)	-0.048*** (0.007)	-0.001 (0.003)	0.156*** (0.031)		-0.018*** (0.007)
Age	0.007*** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.002)	0.002** (0.001)	-0.039*** (0.008)	0.074*** (0.012)	-0.006*** (0.002)
Indiv-loan	-0.098 (0.061)	0.028 (0.032)	-0.008 (0.048)	0.025 (0.018)	0.285 (0.210)	-0.014 (0.314)	-0.109** (0.043)
Leverage	0.000 (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.001)	0.012 (0.007)	0.007 (0.011)	0.002 (0.002)
Bank-regul	-0.065*** (0.024)	0.006 (0.012)	-0.032* (0.019)	0.012 (0.007)	-0.048 (0.083)	0.265** (0.121)	-0.036** (0.017)
NBFI	-0.032 (0.045)	-0.082*** (0.023)	-0.152*** (0.035)	0.021 (0.013)	-1.250*** (0.152)	-0.602*** (0.222)	0.002 (0.031)
Voluntary-sav	0.075*** (0.024)	-0.010 (0.012)	0.038** (0.019)	0.025*** (0.007)	0.092 (0.082)	0.422*** (0.120)	0.017 (0.017)
Mandatory-sav	-0.040 (0.029)	0.033** (0.015)	0.076*** (0.023)	0.001 (0.009)	0.103 (0.101)	0.152 (0.149)	0.136*** (0.021)
HDI	-0.258* (0.147)	0.248*** (0.076)	0.601*** (0.115)	0.087** (0.044)	-3.064*** (0.503)	0.030 (0.736)	-0.017 (0.103)
Heritage	-0.003 (0.002)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.003** (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.011* (0.006)	-0.000 (0.009)	0.002* (0.001)
Constant	0.416* (0.252)	0.758*** (0.129)	0.743*** (0.196)	-0.048 (0.075)	2.374*** (0.857)	8.043*** (1.114)	1.205*** (0.177)
Region dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Model statistics							
Observations	416	416	416	416	416	416	416
R-squared	0.234	0.343	0.285	0.212	0.358	0.382	0.501
χ^2 statistic	133.61	297.46	222.42	113.33	280.86	256.97	436.02
Prob > χ^2	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Correlation of residuals							
	ROE	OEP	PYIELD	PAR>30	ALS-GDP	Cred-clients (ln)	Female-perc
ROE	1.000						
OEP	-0.065	1.000					
PYIELD	0.169	0.724	1.000				
PAR>30	-0.338	-0.204	-0.231	1.000			
ALS-GDP	-0.023	-0.268	-0.277	0.083	1.000		
Cred-clients (ln)	0.196	0.233	0.275	-0.284	-0.294	1.000	
Female-perc	-0.013	0.106	0.150	-0.018	-0.076	0.170	1.000
Breusch-Pagan Chi square = 551.620			P-value = 0.000				

Table 5 presents the joint estimates of microfinance performance on the percentage of shares held by international owners in internationally initiated MFIs (Perc-shares-init) and the set of control variables using the seemingly unrelated regression equations (SURE). All regressors are defined in Table 1. As proxies for financial performance, we apply ROE, i.e., the return on equity; OEP, i.e., the ratio of total operational expenses to the total loan portfolio; PYIELD, i.e., the ratio of interest income over total loan portfolio; and PAR>30, i.e., the share of MFI loan portfolio that is over 30 days in arrears. As a proxy for social performance, ALS-GDP is the average loan size (scaled by GDP per capita), Cred-clients (ln) is the log of the total number of credit clients, and Female-perc is the percentage of female clients. ***, **, and * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. Standard errors appear in parentheses.

Appendix A

Countries and region of origin of large international shareholders

Country of origin			Region of origin		
Country	Number of international shareholders	Percentage	Region	Number of countries	Percentage
Bangladesh	1	2.13	Africa	2	4.26
Belgium	2	4.26	Asia	2	4.26
Canada	1	2.13	Europe	24	51.06
Cayman Islands	1	2.13	North America	17	36.17
France	3	6.38	Other	1	2.13
Germany	1	2.13	South America	1	2.13
Indonesia	1	2.13			
Italy	2	4.26			
Luxembourg	1	2.13			
Mauritius	1	2.13			
Netherlands, The	6	12.77			
Norway	2	4.26			
Other	1	2.13			
South Africa	1	2.13			
Spain	1	2.13			
Switzerland	1	2.13			
United Kingdom	5	10.64			
United States	15	31.91			
Venezuela	1	2.13			
Grand Total	47	100.00		47	100.00

Appendix B

The frequency and percentage of MFIs in the dataset

Country	Number of MFIs	Percentage
Albania	1	0.83
Argentina	1	0.83
Armenia	2	1.67
Azerbaijan	4	3.33
Benin	1	0.83
Bolivia	2	1.67
Bosnia Herzegovina	1	0.83
Cambodia	11	9.17
Cameroun	1	0.83
China	2	1.67
Colombia	1	0.83
Dominican Republic	2	1.67
El Salvador	4	3.33
Ethiopia	6	5.00
Georgia	2	1.67
Guinee	2	1.67
Haiti	1	0.83
Honduras	2	1.67
India	1	0.83
Jordan	3	2.50
Kazakhstan	1	0.83
Kenya	7	5.83
Kyrgyzstan	4	3.33
Madagascar	1	0.83
Mexico	9	7.50
Moldova	1	0.83
Mongolia	3	2.50
Mozambique	1	0.83
Nicaragua	1	0.83
Niger	2	1.67
Paraguay	1	0.83
Peru	15	12.50
Philippines	1	0.83
Romania	3	2.50
Russian Federation	1	0.83
Senegal	1	0.83
Tajikistan	6	5.00
Tanzania	4	3.33
Uganda	6	5.00
Zambia	2	1.67
Total	120	100.00